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S U M M A R Y.

1. A flavone colouring matter named amarbelin has been isolated from the seeds of *Cuscuta reflexa*, Roxb.

2. Amarbelin has been shown to be a dihydroxytrimethoxyflavone. Amarbelin gives protocatechuic acid on caustic potash fusion. Demethylation of amarbelin gives a product different from quercetin or morin and named as amarbelitin.

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Spiro-compounds. Part I. A New Route to Spiro-compounds. Synthesis of *cyclo*Hexane-spiro-*cyclopentane*

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The valency deflexion hypothesis has been supported by Thorpe, Ingold and co-workers by the work on the formation and stability of spiro-compounds (*cf.* Thorpe and co-workers, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1080; 1919, 115, 320; 1921, 119, 1199; 1922, 121, 1496; 1926, 2011; Kon, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 810; 1922, 573; Birch, Gough and Kon, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1315; Paul, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 717).

The methods available for the preparation of such compounds are limited in number and a new general method has been described in this paper. This consists in condensing the sodium salt of the dicyano ester (I), formed by the condensation of a ketone-cyanohydrin with ethyl sodiocyanoacetate (Higson and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 1455) with a monohalogenated ester to yield the product (II).

This on hydrolysis gives an acid, the triethylester (III) of which, when subjected to the Dieckmann condensation yields the product (IV).

(R, R' are either alkyl groups or parts of different ring systems and n may have numerical values ranging from 1 to 3).

For the synthesis of *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane* the following method has been adopted. Freshly distilled *cyclohexanone* cyanohydrin is allowed to react with the sodium salt of ethyl cyanoacetate (*cf.* Dickens, Horton and Thorpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 1830), when the sodium derivative of ethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1-cyanoacetate (V) is obtained. It is then allowed to react with ethyl β -chloropropionate when diethyl 1-cyanocyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate is obtained in good yield. When hydrolysed by means of sulphuric acid (70%) the latter yields an anhydride (VI) (corresponding ester is obtained on esterification). The acid anhydride yields 1-carboxycyclohexane-1- α -glutaric acid on treatment with caustic alkali. Triethyl *cyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate*, obtained by esterifying the above acid, gives diethyl *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-3:5-dicarboxylate* (VII), when heated in benzene solution in presence of sodium. This ester gives a violet colouration in alcoholic solution with ferric chloride and it has got a peculiar fruity smell characteristic of the series. This ester on hydrolysis gives *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylic acid* (VIII). It shows all the properties of a keto-acid and on oxidation yields *cyclohexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid*. By

the Clemmensen reduction of the keto-acid (VIII), *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-5-carboxylic acid* is obtained, which gives *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane* (IX) on decarboxylation by heating the calcium salt with lime. This hydrocarbon has previously been obtained by the reduction of *2-ketocyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane* (*Ber.*, 1929, **62**, 2180. *cf.* also *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 353) which in turn is obtained either by treating the reduction product of *cyclopentanone* with sulphuric acid (Maiser, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 2055,) or by the action of sulphuric acid on $\Delta^9:10$ -octahydronaphthalene oxide (Hückel, *Annalen*, 1929, **474**, 121) or by the action of zinc and ethyl bromoacetate on $\Delta^9:10$ -octalin oxide (Clemo and Ormston, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1780).

(V)

or

(VI)

(VII)

(VIII)

(IX)

The crude product obtained by the Clemmensen reduction of *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylic acid* when heated with selenium yields naphthalene. Such a type of ring transformation (*cf.* Clemo and Ormston, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 352), may be explained by supposing that the system migrates to a stable

form at high temperature, the spiro-compound is first transformed into decalin and then dehydrogenation takes place with the formation of naphthalene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Diethyl-1-cyanocyclohexane-1- α -cyanoglutarate.—To a well-cooled solution of freshly distilled cyclohexanone cyanohydrin (186 g.) in absolute alcohol (186 c. c.), a suspension of ethyl sodiocyanoacetate, obtained from ethyl cyanoacetate (168 g.), sodium (33 g.) and alcohol (500 c. c.), was gradually added with vigorous shaking. The mixture after being kept in ice for 6 hours and at room temperature for 3 days, was mixed with ethyl β -chloropropionate (230 g.) and after the initial reaction had abated was boiled under reflux until it was neutral to litmus (about 40 hours). The mixture was filtered and the filtrate diluted with water and extracted with ether, the ethereal solution washed with water, dried and the ether removed. The ester distilled as a viscous liquid, b. p. 220°-25°/8 mm., yield 160 g. (Found: C, 63.4; H, 7.3. $C_{17}H_{24}O_4N_2$ requires C, 63.7; H, 7.5 per cent).

1-Carboxycyclohexane-1- α -glutaric Acid.—The foregoing ester (20 c. c.) could not be hydrolysed with concentrated hydrochloric acid even on prolonged boiling. It was mixed with sulphuric acid (70 %, 120 c. c.) and boiled under reflux for 12 hours. The condenser was removed from the flask from time to time to allow the alcohol formed to escape. The solution was then diluted with water and extracted with ether, and the ethereal solution was treated with sodium carbonate. On acidification of the carbonate solution the compound (VI) was obtained which was heated on a water-bath with a solution of caustic alkali (15%) for 3-4 hours. The alkali solution was then acidified and extracted with ether. After removing ether the product was kept in a desiccator when it solidified. It crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid, m. p. 165° (decomp.), yield 12 g. (Found: C, 56.2; H, 6.8. $C_{12}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 55.8; H, 6.9 per cent).

The crude acid anhydride (II) was esterified by passing alcohol vapour through a mixture of it in alcohol containing sulphuric acid. The product obtained after working up in the usual manner was found to distill in vacuum, but solidified on attaining the laboratory temperature. It was crystallised from ether, m. p. 46°. (Found: C, 62.5; H, 7.4. $C_{14}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 62.6; H, 7.4 per cent).

Triethyl cyclohexane-1-carboxylate-1- α -glutarate was obtained in an almost quantitative yield from the acid by the alcohol vapour method. In a typical experiment the acid (25 g.), absolute alcohol (75 c. c.) concentrated sulphuric acid (7 c. c.), 3 litres of vapourised alcohol (3-4 hours) gave 26 g. of the ester, b. p. $164^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, $63\cdot7$; H, $8\cdot6$. $C_{28}H_{30}O_6$ requires C, $63\cdot1$; H, $8\cdot8$ per cent).

Diethyl cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-3:5-dicarboxylate, (VII).—A mixture of the foregoing ester (10 g.) and granulated sodium (1·2 g.) in dry benzene (25 c. c.) was refluxed for 10 minutes to start the reaction. The heating was discontinued until the vigour of the reaction abated and was then continued for 2 hours. After cooling, the product was treated with cold dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene layer was washed with aqueous sodium carbonate and with water, dried and evaporated. The residue in alcoholic solution gave a violet colouration with ferric chloride. The ester was obtained as a pale yellow oil (5 g.), b. p. $174^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, $64\cdot6$; H, $8\cdot0$. $C_{16}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, $64\cdot8$; H, $8\cdot1$ per cent).

cycloHexane-spirocyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylic Acid, (VIII).—The ester (VII) was refluxed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid (20%) for 12 hours and the cooled solution saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether, and the extract washed with water and dried. After removing the ether it was kept in a desiccator when it crystallised as needles, m. p. 102° (after previous softening). (Found : C, $67\cdot5$; H, $8\cdot1$. $C_{11}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, $67\cdot4$; H, $8\cdot1$ per cent).

Ethyl cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one-5-carboxylate, prepared by refluxing a solution of the keto-acid (10 g.) in absolute alcohol (40 c. c.) with the addition of absolute alcohol (5 c. c.) saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride, formed a colourless viscous oil (7 g.), b. p. $132^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found : C, $70\cdot9$; H, $8\cdot2$. $C_{18}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, $69\cdot6$; H, $8\cdot9$ per cent). The *Semicarbazone* crystallised from absolute alcohol, m. p. 201° . (Found : N, $14\cdot6$. $C_{14}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N, $14\cdot9$ per cent).

cycloHexane-spiro-cyclopentane.—The pure keto-acid (5 g.) amalgamated zinc (30 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (45 c. c.) were refluxed for 12 hours, further acid (30 c. c.) was then added and the heating continued for 12 hours. By extraction with ether a product was obtained which even on keeping for a long time in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid did not solidify. This product showed no properties of a ketone but when the calcium salt was heated with lime in

vacuum *cyclohexane-spiro-cyclopentane* was obtained as an oil in a very poor yield. It was fractionated several times and the fraction at 63° - $75^{\circ}/15$ mm. was collected and was converted into a bromo derivative, m. p. 130 - 32° . (Found : Br, 70.3 . Calc. for $C_{10}H_{14}Br_4$: Br, 70.4 per cent).

Dehydrogenation of cycloHexane-spiro-cyclopentane-5-carboxylic Acid.—The crude acid (5 g.) and selenium (25 g.) were heated at 280° - 290° for 20 hours. The temperature was then raised to 330° and maintained for 30 hours. The reaction product was extracted several times with light petroleum (b. p. 40° - 60°). After removing the petroleum the residue was distilled over sodium in vacuum, when after fractionation, a small quantity of naphthalene was obtained, m. p. 80° alone or mixed with an authentic specimen of naphthalene. The picrate melted at 148° - 49° (mixed m. p.)

Oxidation of cycloHexane-spiro-cyclopentane-2-one 5-carboxylic Acid.—The keto-acid (3 g.) was warmed with an excess of concentrated nitric acid until most of the red fumes disappeared. The resulting solution was then boiled for a few minutes and finally evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water and again evaporated; the semi-solid mass, thus obtained, was left on a porous plate and after crystallising from water the *cyclohexane-1:1-dicarboxylic acid* melted at 176° (decomp.) (lit. m. p. 176°). On heating it loses carbon dioxide, giving an acid, m. p. 31° , which proved to be identical with hexahydrobenzoic acid.

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